

Deliverable D8

Validation report on the optimal impedance-based measurement procedure and on physicochemical models of Li-ion battery cells to support residual capacity measurement and qualitative premature sudden death detection of second use Li-ion batteries

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Summary report

D8- Validation report on the optimal impedance-based measurement procedure and on physicochemical models of Li-ion battery cells to support residual capacity measurement and qualitative premature sudden death detection of second use Li-ion batteries

Deliverable D4 of the EMPIR – Project 17IND10 “LiBforSecUse”

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Abbreviations

EIS – Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

NFRA – Nonlinear Frequency Response Analysis

LCT – Life Cycle Test

EoL – End of Life (of a battery cell)

SoH – State of Health (of a battery cell)

Ni-rich NMC - Layered Lithium Nickel Manganese Cobalt oxide with high content of Nickel

LFP – Lithium iron phosphate

GEIS – Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy with current perturbation signal

DC – Direct Current

SoC – State of Charge (of a battery cell)

CC discharge – Constant Current (galvanostatic) discharge

CC-CV charge – Constant Current (galvanostatic) charge followed by an additional Constant Voltage charge [until specified current limit]

SEI – Solid Electrolyte Interface

PE – periodic evaluation

Re(Z) – Real part of impedance

Im(Z) – Imaginary part of impedance

|Z| – Impedance magnitude

1. Introduction

The European metrology project LiBforSecUse project aimed to provide a metrological approach to characterize Lithium-ion batteries that have completed their first life in electric vehicles, but can be used for a second application, for example as a stationary energy storage system, so called second-use (or second-life) batteries. To this end, four impedance-based empirical models have been established on a broad data base of life-cycle-test (LCT) data a commercial 18650 cells (i.e., see deliverables D4 and D5), based on

- Direct analysis of impedance spectra
- Distributed relaxation time analysis
- Equivalent circuit modelling
- Non-linear frequency analysis

After the completion of the models, validation activities have been conducted to assess the validity and robustness of the models. These have been:

Physical models of measured impedance and NFRA spectra have been applied to provide a scientific foundation of the observed behavior of the empirical models. Various types of post-mortem analysis have been conducted to provide numerical input for the physical modelling of some selected battery properties. Furthermore, the evolution of post-mortem parameters with ageing batteries should be qualitatively compared with the evolution of the respective EIS and NFRA parameters to check the consistency of the empirical models with the actual state of the cells under investigation.

Secondly, comparison measurements have been conducted to verify the equivalence of EIS measurements of Li-ion battery cells that are conducted at different institutes and to verify the reproducibility of state-of-health prediction.

Finally, additional LCTs of the 18650 cells have been conducted with cells being cycled under different conditions compared to the data used for model development and training. These data have been used as input to predict SOH with the empirical models and compare the results with conventionally measured SOH values. The aim of these activities was to test the robustness of the models.

This report summarises the validation activities and the main outcomes.

It should be mentioned that further validation activities had originally been planned. Application of the models to 'real life' cells provided by industry was planned as well as the extension of the methodology to modules. In fact, aged cells have been procured from industrial suppliers and stakeholders. Likewise, a life-cycle test of modules has been conducted. Unfortunately, the restrictions imposed on most laboratories by the Covid-19 pandemic has caused some significant delay in the completion of the empirical models, since the models could obviously be established only after the provision of the life-cycle-test data. As a consequence, it has not been possible to conduct all validation measurements as planned despite the project run-time had been extended for 6 months.

Moreover, it must be noted that premature sudden death detection, or to be more precise, accelerated aging, will be addressed in the report of D6. Basically, the data base of the preliminary feasibility study has not been sufficient to come to reliable conclusions. Validation of accelerated aging detection is therefore meaningless at present.

2. Physical modelling

2.1. Impedance spectra

2.1.1. Introduction

As discussed in D5, three empirical EIS-based SOH estimation models have been developed by correlation of raw or processed EIS data to measured SOH. Aging parameters with high sensitivity to SOH were identified for the various methods using correlation analysis. For models trained on data recorded at SOC 100%, these parameters are:

- Direct impedance-based models: four raw impedance points at frequencies between 0.01 Hz and 0.5 Hz
- EC-based model: properties of the lower frequency ZARC feature and diffusive tail
- DRT-based model: properties of the slowest time constant

In all cases, the identified aging parameters address low frequency parts of the spectrum and, for the processed data methods, specifically reference the lowest frequency ZARC (depressed semicircle) feature. This is consistent with visual inspection of impedance spectra at SOC 100% (see D5); the spectra show that with increasing cycle number (and hence decreasing SOH), there is a progressive increase in the resistance and decrease in the characteristic time constant associated with a lower-frequency depressed semicircle. These observations are summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1: (a) Exemplar impedance spectra showing increase in the resistance and decrease in the time constant of a low frequency arc, with increased cycle number. (b) Monotonic dependence with SOH of the equivalent circuit coefficient $R_{ct,2}$, corresponding to the resistance of the low frequency arc in (a).

Since the SOH estimation models are trained empirically from impedance data, they contain no explicit information about the mechanism causing the correlation between SOH and impedance response. Such scientific insight can only be established by interpretation using a physicochemical model, in conjunction with experimental evidence from comparative *post mortem* analysis of fresh and aged cells.

The purpose of this work is to establish a representative physicochemical model of an NMC811-silicon/graphite cell, which can be used to understand the respective SOH and impedance sensitivities with respect to a shortlist of aging mechanisms indicated from the *post mortem* analysis. The model will be parameterised as far as possible with fresh cell *post mortem* data while using supplementary literature data where required. No attempt is made to fit explicitly the cell discharge

curve or impedance response; rather, gross qualitative distinctions are sought between the impact of distinct aging mechanisms upon SOH and impedance.

2.1.2. Physicochemical model

The base physicochemical model is the “Newman model” (1-3). This model constitutes a widely accepted mathematical description of the “traditional” lithium-ion battery, consisting of two porous lithium insertion electrodes separated by a structurally porous but electrochemically inert separator, with all pores filled with a binary monovalent lithium electrolyte in a polar aprotic solvent.

Once the model is established, the discharge curve (and hence capacity within a defined voltage window) and the EIS response at any SOC can be predicted by solving the Newman model equations subject to appropriate boundary conditions. By defining certain parameters of the physical description whose values are altered due to degradation in an aged cell, the implied impact of a certain degradation process on the measured data can be assessed.

2.1.2.1. Model specification

All notation is summarised in Section 0. The system is assumed to be isothermal.

2.1.2.1.1. Geometry

The macroscopic geometry is 1D, parallel to the direction of current flow, with three domains (negative electrode, separator, positive electrode) whose respective thicknesses are L_{neg} , L_{sep} , L_{pos} .

2.1.2.1.2. Charge transport in electron-conducting phase

Electrical current in the electron-conducting (solid electrode) phase obeys Ohm’s law:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{i}_s = -\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\varepsilon_s}{\tau_s} \sigma_s \nabla \phi_s \right) = -i_{v,\text{tot}} \quad (1)$$

$$i_{v,\text{tot},m} = a_m i_{\text{tot},m} \quad (2)$$

Volume fractions of active material are defined from a mass loading, skeletal density and electrode thickness:

$$\varepsilon_{s,m} = \frac{m_{\text{load},m}}{L_m \rho_{s,m}} \quad (3)$$

2.1.2.1.3. Concentrated electrolyte model

A concentrated electrolyte theory is used to describe the non-ideal transport of charge and mass in the electrolyte:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{i}_l = +i_{v,\text{tot}} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\varepsilon_l c_l)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{N}_l = R_l \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{i}_l = -\kappa_{\text{eff},l} \nabla \phi_l + \frac{2\kappa_{\text{eff},l} RT}{F} \left(1 + \frac{\partial \ln f_{\pm}}{\partial \ln(c_l / c_0)} \right) (1 - t_+) \nabla \ln \left(\frac{c_l}{c_{l,0}} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{N}_l = -D_{\text{eff},l} \nabla c_l + \frac{\mathbf{i}_l t_+}{F} \quad (7)$$

The transport coefficients $D_{\text{eff},l}$ and $\kappa_{\text{eff},l}$ are effective properties considering a homogenised porous medium of electrolyte filling the gaps between electrode particles. They relate to the corresponding values for pure electrolyte according to:

$$\frac{f_{\text{eff}}}{f} = \frac{\varepsilon_l}{\tau_l} \quad (8)$$

where f is a transport property.

The volume fraction $\varepsilon_{\text{inert},m}$ contains inert material (binder and conductive additive) that does not contribute to the active electrode-electrolyte interfacial area. Then:

$$\varepsilon_l = 1 - \varepsilon_s - \varepsilon_{\text{inert}} \quad (9)$$

2.1.2.1.4. Single particle model

Both electrodes m are assumed to consist of a porous solid electrode phase permeated by electrolyte, with porosity $\varepsilon_{l,m}$. The solid electrode phase is present as particles of radius $r_{p,m}$ filling a volume fraction $\varepsilon_{s,m}$. The specific surface area of the porous material is given for an assumed spherical particle geometry as:

$$a_m = \frac{3 \varepsilon_{s,m}}{r_{p,m}} \quad (10)$$

Within each particle of electrode m , the solid phase lithium concentration undergoes diffusion in a 1D spherically symmetric geometry as:

$$\frac{\partial c_{s,m}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{N}_{s,m} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{N}_{s,m} = -D_{s,m} \nabla c_{s,m} \quad (12)$$

At the boundary $r = r_p$, the outward flux N_s depends on the local faradaic current density i_{far} as:

$$N_{s,m} = \frac{i_{\text{far},m}}{F} \quad (13)$$

$$i_{\text{tot},m} = i_{\text{far},m} + i_{\text{cap},m} \quad (14)$$

$$R_{l,m} = R_{l,\text{far},m} + R_{l,\text{cap},m} \quad (15)$$

Capacitive current density is expressed using a specific double layer capacitance, $C_{\text{dl},\text{sp}}$:

$$i_{\text{cap},m} = C_{\text{dl},\text{sp},m} \frac{m_{\text{load},m}}{L_m a_m} \frac{\partial (\phi_s - \phi_l - \Delta \phi_{\text{SEI},m})}{\partial t} \quad (16)$$

For the positive electrode, $\Delta \phi_{\text{SEI},m} = 0$. For the negative electrode, the SEI is treated as an ideal resistor and an ideal parallel-plate capacitor, electronically in parallel:

$$i_{\text{tot},\text{neg}} = \Delta \phi_{\text{SEI}} \frac{d_{\text{SEI}}}{\kappa_{\text{SEI}}} + \frac{\varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_{r,\text{SEI}}}{d_{\text{SEI}}} \frac{\partial \Delta \phi_{\text{SEI}}}{\partial t} \quad (17)$$

Capacitance is only considered in the impedance spectrum; for time-domain simulations, it is set to zero since its contribution is negligible.

The faradaic current density obeys the Butler-Volmer equation:

$$i_{\text{far},m} = i_{0,m} \left(\exp\left(\frac{(1-\alpha_m)F}{RT} \eta_m\right) - \exp\left(\frac{-\alpha_m F}{RT} \eta_m\right) \right) \quad (18)$$

$$i_{0,m} = k_{0,m} F \theta_m^{\alpha_m} (1-\theta)^{1-\alpha_m} \left(\frac{c_l}{c_{l,\text{ref}}} \right)^{1-\alpha_m} \quad (19)$$

$$\theta_m \equiv \frac{c_{s,r=r_{p,m}}}{c_{\text{sat},m}} \quad (20)$$

$$c_{\text{sat},m} = Q_{\text{sp},m} \frac{\rho_{s,m}}{F} \quad (21)$$

$$\eta_m = \phi_s - \phi_l - U_m(\theta_m) - \Delta\phi_{\text{SEI}} \quad (22)$$

$$R_{l,\text{far},m} = \frac{a_m i_{\text{far},m}}{F} \quad (23)$$

$$R_{l,\text{cap},m} = -a_m v_{\text{DL},m} \frac{i_{\text{cap},m}}{F} \quad (24)$$

2.1.2.1.5. Boundary conditions

Electrical ground is assumed to apply at $x = 0$:

$$\phi_s = 0 \quad (25)$$

At $x = L_{\text{tot}}$, the current density i_{cell} is galvanostatically controlled:

$$\mathbf{i}_s \cdot \mathbf{n} = -i_{\text{cell}} \quad (26)$$

Positive i_{cell} is defined as a charging current by convention. Total cell current is given:

$$I_{\text{cell}} = i_{\text{cell}} A_{\text{cell}} \quad (27)$$

E_{cell} is then determined as the value of ϕ_s at $x = L_{\text{tot}}$.

The solid phase current density falls to zero at the limits of the porous electrodes, $x = L_{\text{neg}}$ and $x = L_{\text{tot}} - L_{\text{pos}}$:

$$\mathbf{i}_s \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \quad (28)$$

The current collectors are impermeable to the electrolyte salt. Hence, at $x = 0$ and $x = L_{\text{tot}}$:

$$\mathbf{i}_l \cdot \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{N}_l \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0 \quad (29)$$

2.1.2.1.6. Initial conditions

The electrolyte concentration is given a constant initial value of $c_{l,0}$. The initial value of c_s in each electrode is determined based on the defined state-of-charge of the cell as follows. The total cyclable Li content (per unit cell cross-section) available for reversible charge and discharge is given for any condition of the cell as:

$$n_{s,tot} = L_{pos} \varepsilon_{s,pos} c_{s,pos} + L_{neg} \varepsilon_{s,neg} c_{s,neg} \quad (30)$$

This quantity of Li equals the quantity of Li initially present, which is defined from the properties of the positive electrode before the first charge, and the extent of loss of Li during formation cycling ($f_{loss,0}$):

$$n_{s,tot,0} = L_{pos} \varepsilon_{s,pos,0} c_{sat,pos} (1 - f_{loss,0}) \quad (31)$$

Further loss of cyclable lithium (Loss of Lithium Inventory, LLI) during degradation is defined relative to the lithium inventory of the fresh cell after formation:

$$n_{s,tot} = n_{s,tot,0} (1 - f_{loss,deg}) \quad (32)$$

From rearrangement of the above we can write:

$$\theta_{pos} = \frac{\varepsilon_{s,pos,0}}{\varepsilon_{s,pos}} (1 - f_{loss,0}) (1 - f_{loss,deg}) - f_{xs,neg} \theta_{neg} \quad (33)$$

where the instantaneous excess capacity of the negative electrode, $f_{xs,neg}$, is defined:

$$f_{xs,neg} \equiv \frac{L_{neg} \varepsilon_{s,neg} c_{sat,neg}}{L_{pos} \varepsilon_{s,pos} c_{sat,pos}} \quad (34)$$

Hence, for the condition at SOC 0%, the maximum saturation of the positive electrode relates to the minimum saturation of the negative electrode as:

$$\theta_{max,pos} = \frac{\varepsilon_{s,pos,0}}{\varepsilon_{s,pos}} f_{Li} - f_{xs,neg} \theta_{min,neg} \quad (35)$$

For any condition of the cell, there exists a thermodynamic open circuit voltage given:

$$E_{OCV} = U_{pos}(\theta_{pos}) - U_{neg}(\theta_{neg}) \quad (36)$$

SOC 0% is defined at an end-of-discharge voltage E_{EOD} . Inserting (35) into (36) and setting $E_{OCV} = E_{EOD}$ creates an equation from which $\theta_{min,neg}$ can be solved as a function of the other inputs.

Let the cell capacity (per unit cell cross-section) be defined for the fresh cell after formation as $Q_{cell,0}$ (C m²). Then the change in degree of saturation for each electrode is given as:

$$\theta_{max,m,0} - \theta_{min,m,0} = \frac{Q_{cell,0}}{F} \frac{1}{L_m \varepsilon_{s,m,0} c_{sat,m}} \quad (37)$$

where the given quantities are evaluated for $f_{loss,deg} = 0$ and $\varepsilon_{s,pos} = \varepsilon_{s,pos,0}$.

SOC 100% is defined at the end-of-charge voltage E_{EOC} , such that:

$$E_{EOC} = U_{pos}(\theta_{min,pos}) - U_{neg}(\theta_{max,neg}) \quad (38)$$

The properties $\theta_{min,pos,0}$ and $\theta_{max,neg,0}$ are related to the properties $\theta_{max,pos,0}$ and $\theta_{min,neg,0}$ as well as the unknown $Q_{cell,0}$ according to (37). Hence when E_{EOC} is specified, $Q_{cell,0}$ can be found by solving the (38).

To consider a degraded cell, $f_{loss,deg}$ and $\varepsilon_{s,pos}$ are specified to differ from their initial values. Then, there exists an equation analogous to (37):

$$\theta_{\max,m} - \theta_{\min,m} = \frac{Q_{\text{cell}}}{F} \frac{1}{L_m \varepsilon_{s,m} c_{\text{sat},m}} \quad (39)$$

Substituting into (36) allows Q_{cell} to be calculated for the degraded cell. Then, the thermodynamic (OC) state-of-health is defined as:

$$\text{SOH}_{\text{OC}} = \frac{Q_{\text{cell}}}{Q_{\text{cell},0}} \quad (40)$$

Lastly, the initial Li concentration in electrode m is specified from the given SOC:

$$c_{s,\text{neg}} = c_{\text{sat},\text{neg}} \left(\theta_{\min,\text{neg}} + \text{SOC} \cdot (\theta_{\max,\text{neg}} - \theta_{\min,\text{neg}}) \right) \quad (41)$$

$$c_{s,\text{pos}} = c_{\text{sat},\text{pos}} \left(\theta_{\max,\text{pos}} - \text{SOC} \cdot (\theta_{\max,\text{pos}} - \theta_{\min,\text{pos}}) \right) \quad (42)$$

2.1.2.2. Measurement types

2.1.2.2.1. Cell discharge

The initial conditions for cell discharge are defined to be the equilibrated conditions for $E_{\text{cell}} = E_{\text{EOC}}$. Then, the cell is loaded with a discharge current specified as:

$$i_{\text{cell}} = -n_C i_{\text{IC}} \quad (43)$$

where n_C is the C-rate of discharge, and

$$i_{\text{IC}} \equiv \frac{Q_{0,\text{cell}}}{1 \text{ h}} \quad (44)$$

The dynamic discharge capacity of the cell and the dynamic discharge state-of-health are defined as follows:

$$Q_{\text{cell},n_C} = n_C i_{\text{IC}} \int_{E=E_{\text{EOC}}}^{E=E_{\text{EOD}}} dt \quad (45)$$

$$\text{SOH}_{n_C} = \frac{Q_{\text{cell},n_C}}{Q_{\text{cell},0}} \quad (46)$$

2.1.2.2.2. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

EIS can be modelled by perturbing the equations around a given reference solution. The amplitude of the perturbation is assumed to be small, such that the variations are linear and can be treated under a Fourier transformation. All dependent variables are assumed to vary as:

$$u(\mathbf{r}, t) = u_0(\mathbf{r}) + \text{Re} \left\{ \bar{u}(\mathbf{r}) \exp(i\omega t) \right\} \quad (47)$$

where \bar{u} denotes a complex quantity, and the vector \mathbf{r} is the combination of the macroscopic coordinate x and microscopic coordinate r .

A linear perturbation is also applied to the loading boundary condition *equation reference goes here*, so that:

$$\mathbf{i}_s \cdot \mathbf{n} = i_{\text{cell},0} + \Delta i_{\text{app}} \text{Re} \left\{ \exp(i\omega t) \right\} \quad (48)$$

(47) is substituted for each variable into the above equations to yield a set of stationary equations in the complex variables \bar{u} . These equations are solved for various values of the angular frequency $\omega = 2\pi f$.

The numerical simulation is simplified by utilising an analytical impedance relation for the faradaic response of the single particle model, as derived by Meyers et al. (4). Therefore, the EIS solution does not solve numerically in the microscopic dimension.

$$\bar{i}_{\text{far},m} = \frac{\bar{\eta}_{m,\text{const,solid}}}{\frac{RT}{Fi_{0,m}} + \frac{\partial U_m}{\partial \theta_m} \frac{r_{p,m}}{Fc_{\text{sat},m} D_{s,m}} \frac{1}{1 - \gamma_m \coth \gamma_m}} \quad (49)$$

$$\gamma_m = r_{p,m} \sqrt{\frac{i\omega}{D_{s,m}}} \quad (50)$$

Here, the subscript “const,solid” indicates that in the linearisation of overpotential, the variation due to the state-of-charge θ is neglected, since this variation is accounted for explicitly through the second term in the denominator. In the value for η at the linearization point, however, the contribution must be included in order that this value = 0 for perturbation about a zero current condition.

2.1.2.3. Degradation model

Cell degradation is described in a mechanism-agnostic manner by altering cell parameters from their fresh cell reference values as follows:

$$u = \gamma_u u_{\text{ref}} \quad (51)$$

where the value of γ_u is set = 1 for the fresh cell.

Aging metrics γ_u were defined according to the list in Table 1.

Table 1: Aging parameters defined within the physicochemical degradation model

Aging process	Altered quantity u
Loss of active material, positive electrode (LAM _{PE})	$\epsilon_{s,\text{pos}}$
Slower electrode kinetics, positive electrode	$k_{0,\text{pos}}$
Slower transport of inserted Li, positive electrode	$D_{s,\text{pos}}$
Depletion of Li electrolyte	$c_{l,0}$
Loss of lithium inventory (LLI)	$(1 - f_{\text{loss,deg}})$
SEI thickening	d_{SEI}^{-1}

2.1.2.4. Numerical implementation

All equations were implemented and solved in COMSOL 5.6 (COMSOL AB, Stockholm) using the Lithium-Ion Battery physics interface combined with user-defined customisations as required to achieve the specified equations. The linear mesh element size in the macroscopic domain was refined at all boundaries to a size of 100 nm, with a maximum size through the domain thickness of 5 μm and a maximum element growth rate of 1.1. The microscopic domain (galvanostatic discharge simulation only) was resolved with 10 elements with cubic size distribution, more refined towards the outer particle radius. A frequency-dependent mesh convergence analysis was performed to ensure accuracy of the numerical solution to the EIS problem.

2.1.2.5. Parameterisation

The model was parameterised using data extracted from fresh cell *post mortem* measurements, wherever these were available. For other data, representative literature values were used where possible. For simplicity, the positive electrode material was treated as NMC811, and the negative electrode material was treated as pure graphite. Fits to cell capacity and EIS characterisation measurements (described fully in the subsequent part of this report) were used to inform the values of the following quantities at each electrode:

- active material mass loading
- insertion rate constants
- active material specific double layer capacitance

Table 2: Input parameters to the physicochemical model, with values and sources.

Quantity	Value	Description	Source
A_{cell}	95000 mm ²	Cell electroactive area	<i>Post mortem</i> area measurement, fresh cell
$C_{\text{dl,neg}}$	170 mF g ⁻¹	Specific double layer capacitance, negative electrode	Fits to measured EIS (by KIT)
$C_{\text{dl,pos}}$	800 mF g ⁻¹	Specific double layer capacitance, positive electrode	Fits to measured EIS (by KIT)
$C_{\text{l,0}}$	1 M	Initial electrolyte concentration	Representative literature value (5)
$D_{\text{s,neg}}$	6×10^{-14} m ² s ⁻¹	Diffusion coefficient, lithium in particles of insertion material, negative electrode	GITT on samples extracted <i>post mortem</i>
$D_{\text{s,pos}}$	6×10^{-14} m ² s ⁻¹	Diffusion coefficient, lithium in particles of insertion material, positive electrode	GITT on samples extracted <i>post mortem</i>
D_{l}	Interpolated function	Diffusion coefficient, electrolyte	COMSOL data for 3:7 EC:EMC (6)
d_{SEI}	80 nm	Thickness, SEI	Fits to measured EIS (by KIT)
$\frac{\partial \ln f_{\pm}}{\partial \ln (c/c_0)}$	Interpolated function	Activity dependence, electrolyte	COMSOL data for 3:7 EC:EMC (6)
E_{EOC}	4.2 V	End-of-charge voltage	LiBforSecUse LCT plan
E_{EOD}	2.9 V	End-of-discharge voltage	LiBforSecUse LCT plan
F	96485 C mol ⁻¹	Faraday constant	Defined by SI
$f_{\text{loss,0}}$	0.05	Proportion of cyclable Li lost during initial conditioning	Assumed
$k_{0,\text{neg}}$	3.23×10^{-8} m s ⁻¹	Insertion rate constant, negative electrode	Fits to measured EIS (by KIT)
$k_{0,\text{pos}}$	6.10×10^{-9} m s ⁻¹	Insertion rate constant, positive electrode	Fits to measured EIS (by KIT)
L_{neg}	56.3 μm	Negative electrode thickness	<i>Post mortem</i> thickness measurement, fresh cell
L_{pos}	46.6 μm	Positive electrode thickness	<i>Post mortem</i> thickness measurement, fresh cell

Quantity	Value	Description	Source
L_{sep}	12 μm	Separator thickness	<i>Post mortem</i> thickness measurement, fresh cell
$m_{load,neg}$	8 mg cm^{-2}	Mass loading, active material, negative electrode	Best estimate from <i>post mortem</i> thickness and electrode porosity measurements, and electrochemical measurement of cell capacity
$m_{load,pos}$	14 mg cm^{-2}	Mass loading, active material, negative electrode	Best estimate from <i>post mortem</i> thickness and electrode porosity measurements, and electrochemical measurement of cell capacity
n_c	1/3	C-rate (galvanostatic discharge)	LiBforSecUse LCT plan (approximate value)
$Q_{sp,neg}$	372 mA h g^{-1}	Specific capacity, negative electrode active material (graphite)	Standard value
$Q_{sp,pos}$	275 mA h g^{-1}	Specific capacity, positive electrode active material (NMC811)	Standard value
R	8.3145 $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$	Gas constant	Defined by SI
$r_{p,neg}$	8.75 μm	Radius, particles of insertion material, negative electrode	<i>Post mortem</i> scanning electron microscopy measurement
$r_{p,pos}$	5 μm	Radius, particles of insertion material, negative electrode	<i>Post mortem</i> scanning electron microscopy measurement
T	23 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	Temperature	LiBforSecUse LCT plan
t_+	Interpolated function	Transport number, Li^+ in electrolyte	COMSOL data for 3:7 EC:EMC (6)
U_{neg}	Interpolated function	Open circuit potential vs. Li^+/Li , negative electrode active material (graphite)	COMSOL data for graphite, with smoothing to ensure monotonicity (7)
U_{pos}	Interpolated function	Open circuit potential vs. Li^+/Li , positive electrode active material (NMC811)	COMSOL data for NMC811, with smoothing to ensure monotonicity (8)
$v_{DL,neg}$	-0.5	Lithium stoichiometry, capacitive charging, negative electrode	Assumed
$v_{DL,pos}$	-0.5	Lithium stoichiometry, capacitive charging, positive electrode	Assumed
α_a	0.5	Anodic transfer coefficient (both electrodes)	Assumed
α_c	0.5	Cathodic transfer coefficient (both electrodes)	Assumed
ϵ_0	$8.854 \times 10^{-12} \text{ F m}^{-1}$	Vacuum permittivity	Universal constant

Quantity	Value	Description	Source
$\epsilon_{\text{inert,neg}}$	0.025	Volume fraction, inert solids, negative electrode	Assumed
$\epsilon_{\text{inert,pos}}$	0.025	Volume fraction, inert solids, positive electrode	Assumed
$\epsilon_{\text{l,sep}}$	0.5	Electrolyte volume fraction, separator	Representative literature value (9)
$\epsilon_{\text{r,SEI}}$	2.25	Effective permittivity, SEI material	Assumed
K_l	Interpolated function	Electrolyte conductivity	COMSOL data for 3:7 EC:EMC (6)
K_{SEI}	$6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S m}^{-1}$	Ionic conductivity, SEI	Fits to measured EIS (by KIT)
$\rho_{\text{s,neg}}$	2.14 g cm^{-3}	Skeletal density, negative electrode active material (graphite)	Standard value
$\rho_{\text{s,pos}}$	4.71 g cm^{-3}	Skeletal density, positive electrode active material (NMC811)	Standard value
$\sigma_{\text{s,neg}}$	100 S m^{-1}	Electrode conductivity (effective), negative electrode	<i>Post mortem</i> 4-point probe measurement
$\sigma_{\text{s,pos}}$	450 S m^{-1}	Electrode conductivity (effective), positive electrode	<i>Post mortem</i> 4-point probe measurement
$\tau_{\text{l,neg}}$	6	Tortuosity, electrolyte negative electrode	Representative value from literature (10)
$\tau_{\text{l,pos}}$	3	Tortuosity, electrolyte in positive electrode	Representative value from literature (10)
$\tau_{\text{l,sep}}$	5	Tortuosity, separator	Representative literature value (9)
τ_{s}	5	Tortuosity, electrode conduction path	Assumed

2.1.2.6. Summary of notation

Input parameter notation is summarised in Table 2 in the previous section. All other notation is summarised in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Variable notation for the physicochemical model.

Variable	Unit	Description
a_m	m^{-1}	Volumetric electroactive area, electrode m
c_l	mol m^{-3}	Li electrolyte concentration
$c_{\text{s},m}$	mol m^{-3}	Inserted Li concentration, electrode m
$c_{\text{sat},m}$	mol m^{-3}	Saturated inserted Li concentration, electrode m
E_{cell}	V	Cell voltage
f	Hz	Frequency
$f_{\text{xs,neg}}$	1	Instantaneous excess capacity, negative:positive electrode
I_{cell}	A	Cell current
$i_{0,m}$	A m^{-2}	Exchange current density, electrode m

Variable	Unit	Description
$i_{cap,m}$	$A m^{-2}$	Capacitive current density, electrode m
$i_{far,m}$	$A m^{-2}$	Faradaic current density, electrode m
i_l	$A m^{-2}$	Macroscopic current density, electrolyte phase
i_s	$A m^{-2}$	Macroscopic current density, electron-conducting phase
i_{tot}	$A m^{-2}$	Current density (local electroactive area)
$i_{v,tot}$	$A m^{-3}$	Volumetric current density (per unit porous electrode volume)
N_l	$mol m^{-2} s^{-1}$	Molar flux, lithium electrolyte
N_s	$mol m^{-2} s^{-1}$	Molar flux, inserted Li in microscopic dimension
n	1	Outward normal vector
$n_{s,tot}$	$mol m^{-2}$	Li molarity per unit geometric area
$Q_{cell,0}$	C	Fresh cell capacity
$Q_{cell,nC}$	C	Cell capacity evaluated from galvanostatic discharge at nC
R_l	$mol m^{-3} s^{-1}$	Lithium molar reaction source (per unit porous electrode volume)
SOC	1	State-of-charge
SOH	1	State-of-health
γ_m	1	Helper variable, single particle impedance, electrode m
ϵ_l	1	Volume fraction, electrolyte
η_m	V	Activation overpotential, electrode m
ϕ_l	V	Electrolyte potential
ϕ_s	V	Electric potential, electron-conducting phase
$\Delta\phi_{SEI}$	V	Potential drop, solid-electrolyte interphase
ϑ_m	1	Extent of lithiation, electrode m
ω	$rad s^{-1}$	Angular frequency

2.1.3. Aging analysis

Post mortem investigation of aged cells from the reference LCT study revealed evidence for the following degradation processes:

- Loss of active material at the positive electrode (LAM_{PE}), due to Mn leaching and disconnection of active particles
- Gradual increase in secondary particle size at both electrodes
- Progressive growth of solid-electrolyte and cathode-electrolyte interfaces, potentially leading to:
 - Loss of lithium inventory (LLI)
 - Slower Li insertion kinetics

The physicochemical modelling exercise investigated the concurrent impact on EIS and SOH of three candidate processes from the above shortlist: LAM_{PE} , slower Li insertion kinetics of the positive electrode, and LLI. Each process was investigated in isolation; it must be recognised that, in reality, physical mechanisms of degradation can lead to correlated changes in multiple aging metrics. Each metric was investigated over the range $0.7 \leq \gamma_u \leq 1$. For each aging condition, a galvanostatic discharge curve at C/3 (with relation to the fresh cell) and an impedance spectrum at SOC 100% were computed.

Figure 2 shows the impact of aging by LAM_{PE} . The measured SOH at C/3 falls consistently with increased LAM_{PE} , due to the decreased accessible capacity of the positive electrode within the defined voltage window. Concurrently, a significant increase in the impedance of one arc of the EIS is observed. This increased impedance is attributable to the decreased area of the positive electrode accessible for reaction, as well as the altered lithiation of the two electrodes under the SOC 100% condition. The qualitative changes to the impedance spectrum in this case are comparable to those observed in the SOH estimation model formulation.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2: Physicochemical model prediction for variation in electrochemical measurements on an 18650 NMC811-graphite cell under loss of active material at the positive electrode (LAM_{PE}). (a): C/3 galvanostatic discharge; (b): EIS at SOC 100%.

Figure 3 shows the impact of aging by slower insertion kinetics in the positive electrode. In this case, there is evidence for increased impedance in one lower frequency arc in the EIS, but there is no corresponding change to the measured SOH. This is explicable because the activation overpotentials are small for C/3 discharge, and therefore the electrode kinetics play a negligible role in determining the accessible cell capacity. The qualitative disparity between these results and those observed experimentally suggests that interfacial changes in isolation are not a plausible explanation for the progressively increased impedance with decreasing SOH. It is most likely that any interfacial change

occurs concurrently with LAM_{PE} , such that the SOH varies due to the latter process, while impedance varies due to both.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Physicochemical model prediction for variation in electrochemical measurements on an 18650 NMC811-graphite cell under slower kinetics for Li insertion at the positive electrode. (a): C/3 galvanostatic discharge; (b): EIS at SOC 100%.

Figure 4 shows the impact of aging by LLI. In this case, while the SOH decreases, the change to the impedance spectrum is qualitatively distinct from that observed experimentally. In particular, the impedance of the lower frequency arc tends to decrease, due to changes in the cell balancing such

that the SOC 100% condition occurs at a less extreme lithiation state of one or both electrodes. These results suggest that it is less plausible to attribute LLI as the degradation process governing the observed trends in the SOH-impedance relation.

Figure 4: Physicochemical model prediction for variation in electrochemical measurements on an 18650 NMC811-graphite cell under loss of lithium inventory (LLI). (a): C/3 galvanostatic discharge; (b): EIS at SOC 100%.

2.1.4. Conclusion

The impact on SOH and impedance response of an 18650 NMC811-graphite cell has been assessed by formulating a physicochemical model, parameterising it with representative information, and solving under varied conditions quantified using mechanism-agnostic aging metrics. The correlation of decreased SOH to the increased impedance of a lower frequency EIS arc suggests a role for loss of active material at the positive electrode, in the 70% < SOH < 95% range; this is one of the candidate degradation processes also suggested by *post mortem* analysis, and is a known degradation process for NMC811 electrodes (11).

This analysis cannot conclusively rule out concurrent contributions from loss of lithium inventory and/or from slower kinetics due to SEI/CEI formation; on the basis of the qualitative trends indicated from the physicochemical model prediction, however, these processes are considered to be unlikely to occur in isolation. It is also important to recognise that (as noted in D5) the SOH estimation models do not necessarily correlate SOH to the specific physicochemical process controlling capacity loss; rather, they depend upon impedance, which may vary due to separate physicochemical processes that evolve concurrently with capacity loss, at a defined rate during cell aging.

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2.2. NFRA spectra

This section reports the model-based assessment at cell level based on a physical battery model, which includes the simulation of NFR spectra. The simulation will be based on the measurement data from the life cycle experiment, specifically cell KIT-06 from LCT 1.04. The simulation results will be used to assess the physicochemical roots of the observed degradation. The model and, indirectly, the parameters will be additionally verified with the results of the various postmortem analysis data.

2.2.1. Newman battery model

The battery model that is implemented in this work is the Newman type battery model known as Pseudo-two-Dimensional (P2D) model, which is introduced by Doyle et al. (Doyle, Fuller, & Newman, 1993). This battery combines both porous electrode theory and the concentrated solution theory. As the name suggests, the modelled electrode is discretized along the x-direction and within each element active material is modelled as spherical particle with defined discretization along r-direction as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: P2D battery model introduced by Doyle et al. (Doyle, Fuller, & Newman, 1993).

Within the active material in the radial direction, the solid-state Li^+ ions concentration c_s in the electrodes is solved via Fick's law of diffusion for spherical particles,

$$\frac{\partial c_s(r)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(D_s r^2 \frac{\partial c_s(r)}{\partial r} \right) \quad (52)$$

with D_s is the diffusion coefficient in active material, r is the radial coordinate and t is the time.

Meanwhile, the liquid-phase Li^+ ions concentration c_e in the electrolyte and in the separator is computed based on the conservation of Li^+ ions in x-direction across the battery,

$$\epsilon_e \frac{\partial c_e(x)}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D_{e,\text{eff}} \frac{\partial c_e(x)}{\partial x} \right) + (1 - t_p) \frac{j^{\text{Li}}(x)}{F} \quad (53)$$

whereby ϵ_e is the electrode porosity, $D_{e,\text{eff}}$ is the effective diffusion coefficient in electrolyte, t_p is the lithium transference number, F is the Faraday's constant, x is the linear coordinate orthogonal to the plain electrode area and j^{Li} is the de-/intercalation current density.

The solid-state potential ϕ_s in the electrodes is derived from Ohm's law,

$$j^{\text{Li}}(x) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\sigma_{s,\text{eff}} \frac{\partial \phi_s(x)}{\partial x} \right) \quad (54)$$

with $\sigma_{s,\text{eff}}$ is the electrical conductivity of solid phase and ϕ_s is the potential of the solid phase.

The liquid-phase potential (Φ_e) in the electrolyte and in the separator is calculated using Kirchhoff's and Ohm's laws,

$$j^{\text{Li}}(x) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(-\sigma_{e,\text{eff}} \frac{\partial \phi_e(x)}{\partial x} \right) - 2 \frac{RT}{F} (t_p - 1) \sigma_{e,\text{eff}} \frac{\partial \ln(c_e(x))}{\partial x} \quad (55)$$

whereby $\sigma_{e,\text{eff}}$ is the effective electrical conductivity of the electrolyte, ϕ_e is the potential of the electrolyte, t_p is the lithium transference number, F is the Faraday's constant, R is the gas constant and T is the temperature.

The de-/intercalation current density j^{Li} at the cathode side is described by the Butler-Volmer kinetics as shown below,

$$j^{\text{Li}} = a_{s,\text{ca}} F k_{\text{ca}} c_{\text{max}} (1 - x_{\text{ca}})^{\alpha_{b,\text{ca}}} \left(\frac{c_e}{c_{\text{ref}}} \right)^{\alpha_{f,\text{ca}}} x_{\text{ca}}^{\alpha_{f,\text{ca}}} \left[\exp \left(\frac{\alpha_{f,\text{ca}} F}{RT} \eta_{\text{ca}} \right) - \exp \left(-\frac{\alpha_{b,\text{ca}} F}{RT} \eta_{\text{ca}} \right) \right] \quad (56)$$

with $a_{s,\text{ca}}$ is the volumetric specific surface area of cathode, k_{ca} is the rate constant for the cathodic de-/intercalation reaction, c_{max} is the maximum Li concentration in cathode, c_e is the Li^+ concentration in electrolyte, c_{ref} is the Li^+ concentration under reference condition, x_{ca} is the surface loading on cathode, $\alpha_{f/b,\text{ca}}$ is the transfer coefficient of de-/intercalation reaction and η_{ca} is the overpotential.

On the anode side, the P2D battery model is extended to include the typical formation of the solid-electrolyte interface (SEI) on anode (Witt, Röder, & Krewer, 2022). Due to the formation of SEI layer, additional interface is introduced on the anode surface and therefore results in additional transport processes of Li^+ ions as shown in the following figure 6.

Figure 6: interfacial processes that are considered in the adapted P2D battery model with formation of SEI layer (Witt, Röder, & Krewer, 2022).

At the SEI/electrolyte interface, the de-/solvation process takes place, which describes the association or removal of solvent component from the Li^+ ions. The faradaic current density resulted from this process can be determined by computing the net rates between the forward and backward reactions,

$$j_{\text{SEI/el}} = a_{s,\text{an}} F \left[\theta_{\text{SEI}} \Gamma_{\text{SEI}} k_{f,\text{SEI}} \exp \left(\frac{\alpha_{f,\text{SEI}} F}{RT} \Delta \phi_{\text{SEI/el}} \right) - a_{\text{el}} (1 - \theta_{\text{SEI}}) \Gamma_{\text{SEI}} k_{b,\text{SEI}} \exp \left(-\frac{\alpha_{b,\text{SEI}} F}{RT} \Delta \phi_{\text{SEI/el}} \right) \right] \quad (57)$$

whereby $j_{\text{SEI/el}}$ is the current density due to de-/solvation, $a_{s,\text{an}}$ is the volumetric specific surface area of anode, θ_{SEI} is the surface coverage at the SEI/electrolyte interface, Γ_{SEI} is the total surface sites at the SEI/electrolyte interface, a_{el} is the Li^+ ion activity in electrolyte, $\Delta \phi_{\text{SEI/el}}$ is the potential difference between two phases, i.e., SEI and electrolyte, $k_{f/b,\text{SEI}}$ is de-/solvation rate constant, $\alpha_{f/b,\text{SEI}}$ is the transfer coefficient of de-/solvation process.

After that, de-/intercalation process takes place at the interface between SEI/electrode and the faradaic current density resulted from de-/intercalation process can be similarly described analog to the de-/solvation process,

$$j_{an/SEI} = a_{s,an} F \left[a_{Li,an} (1 - \theta_{an}) \Gamma_{an} k_{f,an} \exp\left(\frac{\alpha_{f,an} F}{RT} \Delta\phi_{an/SEI}\right) - a_v \theta_{an} \Gamma_{an} k_{b,an} \exp\left(-\frac{\alpha_{b,an} F}{RT} \Delta\phi_{an/SEI}\right) \right] \quad (58)$$

with $j_{an/SEI}$ is the current density due to de-/intercalation process, θ_{an} is the surface coverage at the SEI/electrode interface, Γ_{an} is the total surface sites at the SEI/electrode interface, $a_{Li,an}$ is the Li^+ ions activity in electrode, a_v is the lithium vacancy activity in SEI, $\Delta\phi_{an/SEI}$ is the potential difference between two phases, i.e., SEI and electrode, $k_{f/b,an}$ is the rate constant of de-/intercalation process, $\alpha_{f/b,an}$ is the transfer coefficient of de-/intercalation.

As for the non-faradaic current density such as the current density resulted from the double layer charging at the interface, we implement the expression introduced by Legrand et al. (Legrand, et al., 2014), which calculates the potential difference at the interface $\Delta\phi_{interface}$ based on the net current between the total current density input and faradaic current density ($j_{tot} - j_{interface}$), which is in proportion with the surface area a_s and double layer capacitance C_{dl} .

$$\frac{\partial \Delta\phi_{interface}}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{a_s C_{dl}} (j_{tot} - j_{interface}) \quad (59)$$

Transportation through SEI layer is similarly modelled analog to the electrolyte conservation law, where first part describes the diffusivity of lithium ion through SEI due to the concentration difference at two interfaces and the second term here accounts of the source term effects of Li^+ ions that enter SEI via charge transfer chemistry,

$$\frac{\partial c_{SEI}(x)}{\partial t} = -a_{s,an} F D_{SEI} \frac{a_{s,an} \theta_{SEI} \Gamma_{SEI} - a_{s,an} \theta_{an} \Gamma_{an}}{d_{SEI}} + t_{p,SEI} \frac{j_{tot}}{F} \quad (60)$$

with c_{SEI} is the concentration of Li^+ ions in the SEI layer, D_{SEI} is the Li^+ ions diffusivity in SEI, d_{SEI} is the SEI thickness, $t_{p,SEI}$ is the transference of Li^+ ions in SEI.

The total potential loss due to this SEI layer $\Delta\phi_{SEI}$ is computed by correlating the thickness of SEI d_{SEI} with the surface area $a_{s,an}$ and the ionic conductivity κ_{SEI} ,

$$\Delta\phi_{SEI} = \frac{d_{SEI}}{\kappa_{SEI} a_{s,an}} \quad (61)$$

Following are the assumptions to be made for the extended P2D battery model with formation of SEI layer on the anode side:

- each electrode is modelled as spherical particle
- all spherical particles are identical in terms of geometry and chemical/physical properties
- SEI layer is assumed to be uniformly deposited on the electrode surface
- SEI layer is assumed to be homogeneous in chemical composition and physical structure
- SEI is considered as monolayer (no discretization)

2.2.2. Nonlinear frequency response modelling approach

For the nonlinear frequency response (NFR) modelling part, the battery model that was introduced in the previous section is galvanostatically excited with sinusoidal signal with a moderately large current amplitude (Wolff, Harting, Heinrich, Röder, & Krewer, Nonlinear Frequency Response Analysis on Lithium-Ion Batteries: A Model-Based Assessment, 2018) (Wolff, Harting, Heinrich, & Krewer, Nonlinear frequency response analysis on lithium-ion batteries: Process identification and differences between transient and steady-state behavior, 2019), e.g., 2 C.

The voltage output of the battery model is Fourier-transformed from time to frequency domains. Due to the inherent nonlinear nature of the Li-ion battery, the voltage output signals attain no longer a perfect sinusoidal oscillation as shown in the Figure 7. The resulting spectrum in the frequency domain consists of not only fundamental, but also harmonics, which result from the distortion in the output signal.

For the NFR analysis, we only consider the magnitude of the second (Y_2) and third (Y_3) harmonic signals. The signals from fourth (Y_4) harmonic onwards are disregarded due to the bad signal-to-noise ratio.

Figure 7: NFR modelling approach using the Newman battery model extended with SEI formation on the anode.

2.2.3. Life cycle test

For the model assessment, the data set from life cycle test (LCT 1.04) was chosen as both EIS and NFR measurements are available in this data set. Figure 8 shows the state-of-health (SOH) fade of KIT-06 from LCT 1.04 during the life cycle test. Five points of interest at different interval of elapsed cycle were selected. Based on these states of interest, the discharge behaviour, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and nonlinear frequency response analysis (NFR) were assessed using the battery model. By fitting the discharge behaviour, EIS and NFR over the life cycle test using the aforementioned battery model, the fitted parameter quantifies the evolution of the battery internal state, thus the aging behaviour of the Li-ion battery can be better understood.

Figure 8: SOH fade of KIT-06 from LCT 1.04 with five selected points of interest (red diamond) for model assessment. Table on the right-hand side shows the cycle number and the corresponding SOH of the selected points of interest.

2.2.4. Results

2.2.4.1. Discharge behaviour

Figure 9 (LHS) shows the discharge behaviour of cell KIT-06 from LCT 1.04 over the life cycle test. The solid line is the simulated result, and the dashed line is the experimental result. It can be seen that as the cell ages, the capacity reduces. By fitting the discharge behavior, the result identifies that there is a significant loss of active material on the cathode side as compared to the anode side. The initial maximum Li^+ ions concentration at the cathode side has decreased for about 30 % whereas at the anode side, the initial maximum Li^+ ions concentration at the anode side has only reduced for 10 % relative to the initial concentration. Possible causes for this significant loss at the cathode side could be the manganese dissolution that is in qualitative good agreement with the post-mortem analysis at Aalto.

Figure 9: The experimental (dashed) and simulated (solid) discharge behaviour of KIT-06 (LCT 1.04) at the five selected points of interest (LHS) with the fitted active material losses on anode and cathode respectively (RHS)

2.2.4.2. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

Using the EIS, the losses from the underlying individual processes in the Li-ion cell can be better identified and quantified. As shown in Figure 10, the impedance spectrum comprises of two semicircles. The semicircle at the high frequency (≈ 100 Hz) can be attributed to the transport losses through and at the SEI layer while the semicircle at the low frequency (< 1 Hz) is due to the charge transfer process at the interface between electrode/electrolyte interface.

As cell ages, the semicircle at high frequency which is subjected to the transport losses in SEI layer increase insignificantly as compared to the semicircle at low frequency. Instead, a shift of the spectrum at the high frequency is more significant.

By fitting the impedance at the high frequency range, the results in figure 15 suggest that the thickness of the SEI layer has increased about six times larger as compared to the pristine state. Meanwhile, the ionic conductivities of the SEI drastically decreases by one order of magnitude mainly at the later stage of the ageing, which could be the reason of for the significant shift as observed earlier. Nevertheless, there could be some other reason such as the increase in contact resistance between electrode and current collector or the decrease in ionic conductivity of the electrolyte. However, these contributions cannot be uniquely and separately identified via EIS. In this simulation case, both contributions were assumed to remain constant, and all the impedance increase at high frequency is attributed to the SEI effect. It is important to consider the contact resistance into the cell aging in the future.

Figure 10: Experimental (dashed) and fitted (solid) EIS of KIT-06 (LCT 1.04) at the five selected points of interest over the life cycle test. Ohmic shift is observed at the higher frequency range of the EIS.

Figure 11: The fitting results of the high frequency range of EIS that indicates the evolution of physical properties of the SEI.

The growth of the semicircle in the lower frequency (< 1 Hz) is attributed to the charge transfer reaction at the cathode side according to the post-mortem analysis, i.e., three electrode set-up measurement by KIT. Possible reasons for the impedance increase in the cathodic charge transfer reaction could be the reduction in the reaction rate due to the loss of active material loss, e.g., the dissolution of manganese. The fitting result in Figure 12 indicates that the reaction rate significantly reduces and simultaneously the capacitance value also decreases. This signifies that the reaction become more slower and the SEI interface losses its capacity to store charges as well. In this simulation case, the specific surface area of the cathode side is assumed to remain constant throughout the aging study, which might probably not be the case.

In second simulation case, the rate of the charge transfer process is assumed to remain constant while the specific surface area is allowed to be fitted during aging. The fitting result in Figure 13 similarly indicates that the specific surface area drastically decreases while the capacitance increase for this simulation case. Principally, the impedance increase in the lower frequency range could also be the combination of both effects from the decrease in specific surface area and charge transfer rates. However, this cannot be easily identified purely based on only one type of experiment. Additional post-mortem measurement like measuring the remaining available specific surface area is needed in order to aid in identifying the contribution of one factor, so that the other parameter can be quantified via impedance fitting.

Figure 12: Simulation case 1 for the impedance increase in the lower frequency range of EIS is mainly attributed to the reduction in the kinetic of the cathodic charge transfer process as well as the double layer capacitance.

Figure 13: simulation case 2 for the impedance increase in the lower frequency range of EIS is assumed to purely originates from the reduction in the specific surface area and the increase in the double layer capacitance.

2.2.4.3. Nonlinear Frequency Response Analysis

Based on the parameter set that obtained from the previous fitting exercises, the NFR spectra is simulated, and the result is shown in Figure 14. It is shown that with the exiting parameter set, a good match between experimental and simulated Y_3 can be obtained. However, discrepancies between experimental and simulated Y_2 are observed.

From the previous study and publication from other research groups (Wolff, Harting, Röder, Heinrich, & Krewer, 2019) (Murbach & Schwartz, 2017), it is identified that Y_2 is mainly influenced by the symmetry of the charge transfer process. When the charge transfer process shifts away from symmetrical behaviour, i.e., charge transfer coefficient is not equal to 0.5, this will eventually cause Y_2 to increase. Therefore, this could be the case for the discrepancies that is observed in Figure 14, especially in the late aging stage.

To improve the fitting for NFR spectra, charge transfer coefficients were taken into account. There are in total two sets of transfer coefficients that give a good fit to both experiment and simulation. Both of these two parameter sets show that the charge transfer coefficient deviates from the symmetrical value, i.e., 0.5, either more preference in oxidation or reduction direction. However, preference in oxidation reaction during degradation is reported by Murbach et al. (Murbach & Schwartz, 2017).

Figure 14: The fitted NFR spectra based on the parameter set that is obtained from the fitting of discharge behaviour and EIS with no change in the charge transfer coefficient ($\alpha=0.5$).

Figure 15: The improvised NFR fitting by considering the change in charge transfer coefficient during the aging study ($\alpha \neq 0.5$).

2.2.5. Conclusion

In general, a qualitative model-based assessment was conducted. Through fitting with different experimental results, the changes in the internal states of the cell during aging study can be estimated. Following are the points that could be summarized from the model-based assessment:

- Cathode degradation is more dominant:
 - The loss of active material due to the dissolution of transition metals, e.g., manganese, which causes the reduction in cell capacity or state-of health (SOH)
 - The significant decrease in the rate of charge transfer process, which causes the impedance in the lower frequency range to increase
- Anode degradation could be due to
 - SEI thickness increases and cause the impedance to increase in the higher frequency range
 - The decrease in the ionic conductivity of SEI leads to the ohmic shift of the impedance spectrum.

Further, it is showed that through impedance fitting is actually not sufficient to uniquely characterize the aging behaviour of the cell. Especially at the late aging stage, the symmetrical charge transfer coefficient no longer holds, i.e., $\alpha \neq 0.5$. As an outlook, the degradation in the electrolyte chemistries or properties as well as the contact resistance should be considered, whereby these contributions were assumed to be remains constant throughout the aging study in this model-based assessment.

2.2.6. References

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3. Comparison measurements

A more detailed comparison report, including the comparison of impedance standards and further data files, can be found at the LiBforSecUse Repository at Zenodo.org.

3.1. Comparison of impedance spectra of a commercial 18650 cell

The participants have been asked to measure the capacity and an impedance spectrum of a commercial 18650 cell (Si-graphite anode/NMC cathode) at full state-of-charge (SOC100) and half charge (SOC50). The cell and the fixture have been provided by NPL. The measurement conditions have been thoroughly defined in a technical protocol. Basically, the conditions have been the same as defined for the life cycle tests (LCT) of the 18650 cells conducted for the LiBforSecUse project. Therefore, NPL had provided one of the aged cells of their LCT (state-of-health (SOH) around 70%) with respect to the nominal capacity.

3.1.1. Results

The measured impedance spectra at SOC100 are shown in figure 16. Obviously, the measured spectra differ significantly. Even though a difference had been expected to some extent, the strong difference between the spectra was surprising, given the emphasis that has been put on the definition of reproducibility conditions. It must be noted that impedance data at SOC100 have not been corrected for any calibration bias due to the large differences, nor have measurement uncertainties been assigned.

Figure 16: Nyquist-plot of impedance spectra of the 18650 measured at SOC100.

Parameter	JRC	KIT	NPL	PTB
Measured capacity /Ah	2,164	2.159	2.142	2.173
DC-current capacity measurement	1,25	1.25	1.25	1.25
Measurement temp. /°C	23	23	23	23
number of refresh cycles before measurement	5	0	1	1
EIS AC-current amplitude	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
SOC100 adjustment: charge current of CC step /A	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.25
Nominal SOC100 adjustment: cut-off voltage of CC step /V	4,2	4,2	4.2	4.2
SOC100 adjusted with CV step / yes,no	yes	yes	yes	no
if yes, cut-off current of CV step /A	0.3	0.3	0.3	n/a
voltage SOC 50 /V	3.785	3.786	3.753	3.74

Table 4 Measurement parameters

Table 4 summarises the most relevant parameters reported by the institutes. Even though, there are a few differences, none of them can reasonably be assumed responsible for the differences seen in the spectra. At least, there seems to be no systematic correlation. For instance, PTB omitted the CV step for SOC100 adjustment, while NPL has conducted the CV step just like the other institutes did. Nevertheless, NPL spectra are closer to PTB results as to those of the other two institutes. Similar considerations hold for other deviations of the measurement parameters. However, impedances are rather sensitive from the state of charge at SOC 100, especially for aged cells. Thus, it is very likely that the significant sensitivity of impedance spectra from SOC is responsible for the differing spectra.

The assumption sensitivity at SOC100 being the reason for the deviation rather than uncertainties due to the measurement is also supported by the much better results at SOC50. The corresponding spectra are shown in figure 17. Except the JRC results¹, these spectra have been corrected for the measurement error estimated by a calibration measurement as described in the measurement protocol. Basically, the correction accounted for the results of the short measurement. Additionally, measurement uncertainties were assigned to the impedances. More information on the uncertainty of low-impedance measurements are given in the Guide on RLC/EIS meter low-impedance measurement (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.5959781). Uncertainty contributions assigned to the battery cell are discussed in deliverable D5 of the 17IND10 project. It seems that three institutes show good equivalence, while the results of NPL are differing significantly in the low frequency range for unknown reasons. Therefore, results of NPL have been considered as outliers and have not been included in the subsequent evaluation. Note that the low frequency range is more relevant for the investigation of SOH within the framework of 17IND10 (also see D5 for more details).

Figure 18 shows the degrees of equivalence (DoE) of the real and the imaginary parts of the measured spectra in dependence of frequency at SOC50. The dashed lines show the minimal and maximal expanded ($k=2$) uncertainties of the DoEs of the three institutes. The arithmetic means of the impedances have been used as comparison reference values. The uncertainties of the DoEs

¹ JRC didn't calibrate the impedance meter

considered the measurement uncertainties of the individual results and the standard deviation of the results of the three institutes. On average the (mean) uncertainty of the measurement results is roughly twice the spread of the results of the institutes (expressed by the standard deviation).

Figure 17: Nyquist-plot of impedance spectra of the 18650 measured at SOC50.

Figure 18: Degrees of Equivalence of the real (above) and imaginary (below) parts of the impedance spectra in dependence of frequency at SOC50.

At high frequencies above 1 kHz, the impedances begin to differ significantly. This is due to the large uncertainties introduced by mutual inductive coupling of the various parts of the measurement set-up, which is typical for low-impedance measurement (also see ref. [5]). This can also be seen in the Nyquist-plots in figs. 37 & 38. In the middle range (0.1 to 100 Hz), which is most relevant for the analysis of electrochemical processes, resistances and reactances show good equivalence, which is in range of 30 μOhm . Moreover, it is interesting to note that the equivalence of reactances is better than that of resistances (24 μOhm standard deviation compared to 34 μOhm on average) in the mid frequency range (0.1 to 100 Hz). In this frequency range, reactances mainly result from the formation of double layer capacities, while resistances are dominated by charge transfer reactions. Consequently, capacitive effects seem to be more stable than resistive. The slightly increased, but still acceptable, difference seen at the low frequency end is due to instabilities of the diffusive properties of the cell, which is presumably affected by timely and spatially inhomogeneous temperature variations during the measurement.

Obviously, the measurement results are consistent with the reported measurement uncertainties and the spread of the results. Even though SOC is more difficult to adjust than SOC100, the

impedances appear to be significantly less sensitive to SOC adjustment. Note that SOC 50 adjustment also includes the uncertainties of SOC 100 adjustment, since SOC100 is the reference point for any SOC adjustment. Moreover, the good equivalence also suggests that the measurement uncertainties assigned to the individual results, and that dominate the uncertainty of the DoEs for the most part, might be overestimated to some extent.

3.1.2. Conclusion

Impedance spectra are extremely sensitive to the state-of-charge at SOC 100. Even under thoroughly defined reproducibility conditions the degree of equivalence is quite poor. This might be due to the rather low SOH of the cell under investigation. The sensitive of EIS at SOC 100 of a newer cell should be investigated, since it can be expected that the sensitivity is significantly small for cells aged less. Moreover, reproducibility conditions should be reconsidered at SOC 100. At SOC 50, and presumably at other SOC's between 20 and 90, the equivalence has been shown being in the range of a few tens of μOhms . The cell under investigation had impedances around 10 mOhm. High energy cells show impedances in the range of 1 mOhm in the frequency range of interest. Hence, battery cell investigations by means of EIS can be performed with a relative reproducibility of in the order of 1% or better. Measurement uncertainties of low-impedance battery cells seem to be overestimated to some extent.

3.2. Comparison of SOH prediction.

The main goal of the LiBforSecUse project has been the development of a validated method to predict the residual capacity of battery cells and modules based on impedance measurements. To this end, three empirical models have been developed to calculate the SOH from direct impedance analysis, from a distributed relaxation time (DRT) analysis and from equivalent circuit (EC) modelling (see deliverable D5 for details). As a final validation of the methods, the impedance spectra measured in section 3.1 have been used as input data for the models and the SOH values have been calculated with all three models. Residual capacities have been calculated from the SOH values with respect to a capacity value of 2723 mAh, which has been the measured average capacity of the 18650 cells at the beginning of the life cycle tests of the project. Finally, the predicted values have been compared with the actual residual capacity values. The participating institutes have therefore also measured the capacity of the 18650 by integrating the discharge current of a full discharge cycle.

3.2.1. Results

The results are shown in table 2a – 2d. The last column on the right hand-side of tables 2b -2c show two times the route-mean-square values (RMS) of the cross-validation of the life cycle data used to estimate the expanded uncertainty of the model (see D5).

Institute	actual capacity
	mAh
JRC	2163
KIT	2159
PTB	2173
NPL	2142

Table 5a Results of capacity measurements

Institute	predicted SOH	predicted capacity	deviation	2 x RMS
		mAh	%	%
JRC	0.83	2248.58	3.96	1.5
KIT	0.82	2241.26	3.81	1.5
PTB	0.88	2393.93	10.17	1.5
NPL	0.87	2369.29	10.61	1.5

Table 5b Model for SOH prediction: direct impedance analysis

Institute	predicted SOH	predicted capacity	deviation	2 x RMS
		mAh	%	%
JRC	0.82	2225.16	2.87	2.3
KIT	0.81	2208.55	2.29	2.3
PTB	0.88	2389.45	9.96	2.3
NPL	0.87	2363.67	10.35	2.3

Table 5c Model for SOH prediction: DRT analysis

Institute	predicted SOH	predicted capacity	deviation	2 x RMS
		mAh	%	%
JRC	0.81	2212.46	2.29	2.4
KIT	0.81	2212.00	2.45	2.4
PTB	0.87	2357.98	8.51	2.4
NPL	0.87	2365.81	10.45	2.4

Table 5d Model for SOH prediction: EC modelling

The predicted residual capacities of PTB and NPL deviate significantly from the actual values. For all SOH models, the deviation is significantly larger than the uncertainty assigned to the model. Just like in this comparison, PTB and NPL life cycle test data of the 18650 cells have shown significant deviation from those of the other institutes. Therefore, they had not been used for model development. The results of this comparison seem to confirm that there is some kind of bias that must be evaluated. On the other hand, the comparison results of the DRT and EC analysis of KIT and JRC are reasonably consistent with the RMS values, which basically confirms the validity of the methods. The direct impedance analysis shows a deviation also for the JRC and KIT results. However, this method involves reference of the selected impedance ageing-parameters of the aged cell, to the same aging-parameters of the fresh cell. The latter have not been available for the comparison, which explains the deviation.

3.2.2. Conclusion

The results of the comparison measurements basically confirm the results of the cross-validation analysis. The SOH of a battery cell can be predicted with an uncertainty of less than 3 %, which has been the target uncertainty of this project.

3.3. Final remark

It must be emphasized that this comparison is the first interlaboratory comparison of impedance measurements in the low mOhm range (standards as well as battery cells) that has ever been conducted. It was the intention to get a first insight into the equivalence of the results and to gain experience in the conduction of such a comparison. It had therefore the quality of a pilot study rather than that of a key comparison. Consequently, the evaluation has been driven by practicality and feasibility to achieve these goals rather than following strict rules for uncertainty, comparison reference value calculation and degree of equivalence calculation, which could not properly be applied because of the diversity of the reported values. Even though the results of this comparison are therefore subject to some uncertainty they are nevertheless metrologically sound enough to provide useful insight in the assessment of low-impedance measurements of Li-ion batteries. Furthermore, it supports the validity of the impedance-based methods to estimate the residual capacity with an uncertainty of 3% as stated in the scientific objectives of the project (i.e. O2).

4. SOH prediction with alternative LCT input data

Four SOH estimation models using frequency-response data have been presented and discussed in D5. These models comprise three models developed using different methods for utilising electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) data recorded at 100% SOC: direct impedance-based model, equivalent circuit (EC)-based model, distribution of relaxation times (DRT)-based model. Additionally, a nonlinear frequency response analysis (NFRA)-based model was trained; this model uses data recorded at 80% SOC.

The SOH estimation models were trained using only data from life cycle tests (LCTs) under a single reference cycling condition (4 A, 45 °C) at 100% depth-of-discharge (DoD). D5 reports testing of the model performance using testing data from the same data set, using four-fold cross-validation. Additionally, uncertainties are assessed with respect to the reference cycling condition only.

In this report, the robustness of SOH models trained for the reference condition is evaluated using frequency-response data from other life cycle tests (LCTs) that were conducted under different cycling conditions. Specifically, LCTs at different DoDs (30%, 25-75%, 70%, all at 45 °C) and different cycling temperatures (5 °C, 23 °C, 35 °C, all at DoD 100%) will be considered.

4.1. Direct impedance-based SOH model

The direct impedance-based SOH model was used to predict SOH from EIS recorded during LCTs with different DoD and temperature cycling conditions. The performance of the SOH prediction is depicted in Figure 19 and Figure 20.

Figure 19: Performance of the direct impedance-based SOH model for test data with varying DoD.

Figure 20: Performance of the direct impedance-based SOH model for test data with varying temperature.

The SOH prediction results for other cycling conditions are unsatisfactory (average RMS error in SOH prediction > 3 % SOH units, compared to around 0.7 % SOH units under reference conditions; see D5). The worse performance is nonetheless expected, since the model was only trained with the data set from the reference condition. Generally, the predicted SOHs are higher than the measured SOHs in both cases, i.e. the SOH model overestimates the actual SOH of the cells. When comparing Figure 19 and Figure 20, we can see that temperature has a more significant impact on the performance of the SOH model. Cells that were cycled under lower temperature experience possibly different aging mechanisms, with a different impact upon impedance such that they cannot be captured by the current SOH model. The accuracy of SOH prediction decreases with increasing divergence of the test condition from the training condition.

The SOH prediction accuracy for other cycling conditions can be improved by retraining the SOH model using data sets from all cycling conditions. Figure 21 shows that the SOH prediction accuracy is significantly improved after model refinement; the average RMS error is 1.92 % SOH units.

Figure 21: Example of one output from a four-fold cross validation on direct impedance-based model trained using data from LCTs at all DoDs (T = 45 °C).

4.2. EC-based SOH model

Prior to testing, equivalent circuit fitting as described in D5 was used to process the raw impedance data from the additional LCTs. Fit quality remained good in the majority of cases. Data were ignored if the normalised equivalent circuit fit residual was greater than 3×10^{-3} , as it was established during testing the less conservative value of 5×10^{-3} retained some fits that gave extreme outliers.

The performance of the EC-based SOH model for test data with varying DoD is shown in

Figure 22 (RMS error is 3.1% SOH units), and the corresponding results with varying temperature are shown in Figure 23 (RMS error is 5.1% SOH units). Especially at lower SOH, the trend is for overestimation of the SOH, as for the direct impedance-based model. In the case of temperature variation, it is evident that the model performance worsens with increasing deviation from the reference LCT temperature of 45 °C.

Figure 22: Performance of the EC-based SOH model for test data with varying DoD.

Figure 23: Performance of the EC-based SOH model for test data with varying temperature.

As for the direct impedance-based model, retraining with the full data set allows improved performance, as assessed from cross-validation. An example output from a four-fold cross-validation study, inclusive of LCTs at all DoD ($T = 45\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) is shown in Figure 24; the RMS error in this instance is 1.88% SOH units, and the mean from the four-fold cross-validation was 1.77% SOH units. While these errors are larger than for the model tested on the reference LCTs alone (single DoD), they are significantly improved compared to the application of a model trained on one cycling condition to an altered cycling condition.

Figure 24: Example of one output from a four-fold cross validation on an EC-based model trained using data from LCTs at all DoDs ($T = 45\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$).

It was observed during model retraining that the EC-based SOH model trained on multiple LCTs included also (after stepwise regression) contributing terms from the parameter Q_{diff} , which quantifies an aspect of the diffusive tail of the impedance spectrum. By contrast, the SOH model trained on the LCT did not require this input. This is evidence for the flexible nature of EC-based models, whereby scalar quantities representing different spectral features can be included or removed as required to express the SOH correlation inherent to the impedance spectra under different cycling conditions.

4.3. DRT-based SOH model

The impedance spectra of LCTs with varying cycling conditions were evaluated by means of the distribution of relaxation times (DRT) method as described in D5. The same qualitative information could be derived in most of the spectra - five different time constants were identified. The slowest time constant, which is the main contribution to the spectrum, and its associated resistance were used as predictors. The regression model trained with data from reference conditions (described in D5) was used to estimate the SOHs of the LCTs under varied conditions. Figure 7a shows the SOH estimates of the LCTs at varying temperatures plotted against the measured values, 7b those of the measurements with other DoDs.

Figure 25: SOH estimations of LCTs with (a) lower temperatures and (b) varied DoDs

The results of the SOH estimation with the DRT-based model are comparable to those of the other two models (direct impedance based-model and EC-based model). For deviating temperatures, a systematic overestimation occurs at low SOHs. The effect is the more pronounced, the more the temperature deviates from the reference conditions (Figure 25a). Overestimations of the SOH also occur for the depth of discharge variation (Figure 25b.) The mean RMS error of the SOH estimations of the LCTs at different temperatures and varied DoDs is 3.32 % in SOH units.

As for the two methods shown previously (direct impedance and EC), the regression model was retrained with a combined data set of the LCTs under reference conditions and under varied conditions. The results of the four iterations of the four-fold cross validation are plotted in Figure 26. The estimates are fairly accurate in the SOH range between 95 % and 80 %. For lower values, individual outliers occur for which the SOH is overestimated. The mean RMSE is 2.24 % SOH units which is slightly higher than for the other methods. The model also has a more pronounced tendency to overestimate the SOH than the EC-based model.

Figure 26

4.4. NFRA-based SOH model

Similarly, the NFRA-based SOH model could not predict SOH of cells that cycled under different condition with satisfying accuracy. As shown in Figure 27, the average RMS error is about 3.01 % SOH units, which is much larger than the prediction error under the reference condition (1.2 % SOH units; see D5). After model refinement, the average RMS error can be lowered to 2.36 % SOH units (Figure 28). Overall, the prediction error following model refinement is still slightly higher than the other impedance-based approaches. This might be due to the smaller quantity of available training data, as NFR measurements was only conducted at KIT, unlike EIS measurements were performed at all participating institutions.

Figure 27: Performance of the NFRA-based SOH model for test data with varying DoD

Figure 28: Example of one output from a four-fold cross validation on NFRA-based model trained using data from LCTs at all DoDs (T = 45 °C).

4.5. Conclusion

SOH estimation models trained using only data from the reference LCTs suffer significant accuracy loss when applied to frequency response data from LCTs under different cycling conditions. RMS error is more than 3 % SOH units for the combined testing data set under different cycling conditions, for all methodologies explored. SOH models trained using data from cycling at 45 °C and DoD 100% generally overestimate SOH from LCTs at lower temperature or reduced discharge [range](#). That is, the net change in cell impedance at high SOC is less than would be expected given the decrease in cell capacity. Prediction quality decreases with increasing divergence from the training condition, especially with respect to cycling temperature.

SOH model performance can be improved by retraining including data from the full set of cycling conditions. By this means, a smaller prediction RMS error with less than 3 % SOH units can be attained.

In general, we project from this validation study that impedance- and NFRA-based SOH estimation models do not incorporate intrinsic information about physical mechanisms. In other words, with respect to operating condition, they interpolate but do not extrapolate. It is possible that a more mature machine learning approach could increase the model robustness; however, the relatively similar performance under validation of all four models, developed using diverse methods, suggests that the limitation is probably intrinsic to the data.

Therefore, we conclude that the general methodology for preparing SOH estimation models from frequency response data should begin with a consideration of target cycling conditions, and that LCTs are carried out under a range of cycling conditions relevant to the target use case. Only through this process will it be possible to validate the application of the model to cells with diverse cycling history.